

PROCEEDINGS OF THE GAMES INTERSECTIONAL SYMPOSIUM

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The symposium brought together artists, researchers, designers, and community organizers working at and within the intersections of games, identity, and justice.

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Social Innovation and Video Games: Exploring Implications for Learning and Teaching

by Patrick Gregori & Milica Marković, University of Klagenfurt

Sliders for Everything (Except Gender): A Critique of Gender Norms in Video Game Character Creators through 'Your Average Character Creator'

by Eileen Carette

Disruption through Strategic Game Design: Challenging Caste Transmission Using Interactive Media

by Srikanth Sundaram

In Other Bodies - Inhabiting the Nonhuman Body in Video Games as a Means for Empathy

by Florian Schäfer

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Sliders For Everything (Except Gender): A Critique of Gender Norms in Video Game Character
Creators through *Your Average Character Creator*

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Have you ever tried to create an avatar that looks like yourself in a video game's character creator? Not an idealized, fantasy version of yourself, but simply an accurate representation of a human body. Were you able to succeed, or did you find yourself staring at yet another conventionally attractive, strictly gender-conforming avatar in their 20s or 30s? Even in games that advertise their customization options, it is quite difficult to make anything else. The problem is even more prominent if the avatar is female—why are the male hobbit-inspired halflings of *Baldur's Gate 3* (Larian Studios 2023) allowed to be pudgy and hairy while the female halflings must have perfect hourglass figures?

Figure 1: *Baldur's Gate 3*'s male and female halflings, taken from Černoša and Ritchie 2024.

The problem is made all the more obvious when creating a transgender or non-binary avatar—even character creators proclaimed to be “progressive” limit customization options based on whether the player initially selects a male or female body type, even when those types are not labelled with gendered terms. Video game character creators often present a very strict view of gender, wherein male and female bodies must follow clearly defined guidelines that distinguish them. These guidelines do not reflect the real diversity in human bodies—in real life, after all, it is possible for a woman to be taller than a man. In order to bring attention to this issue, I created a Twine game called *Your Average Character Creator* (Carette 2025, available at: eyeofthedragon.itch.io/your-average-character-creator). In this game, players go through the process of creating their own character. However, they encounter many obstacles and limitations based primarily on their initial selection of a binary choice—which, in this game, is their hair colour.

Oh, sorry, that's not a valid height! After all, on average, brown-haired people are shorter than blonde people. So you're going to have to be shorter than that. [Try again](#).

Figure 2: Screenshot from *Your Average Character Creator*.

The aim of the game is to bring attention to the flaws in mainstream character creators, by satirizing the way options are limited by arbitrary categories like gender and how these creators push character designs towards beauty standards that are frequently based in prejudice. In this paper, I will discuss the ideas and inspiration behind the game, the areas of research informing its creation, the design process, and improvements made to the game based on player feedback.

Game Background

The game was created as part of a graduate course on how gender is represented in video games. In this class, we discussed how character creators can potentially allow for greater diversity in gender presentation in games—for example, the game *Cyberpunk 2077* (CD Projekt Red 2020) allows players to customize their genitals regardless of the selected gender. In theory, this allows a player to create a transgender avatar. However, in practice, the customization options in these games are still extremely limited by a strict conception of a gender binary and by traditional Western beauty standards. *Cyberpunk 2077* allows for countless body modification options as befitting of its cyberpunk setting—but it does not allow top surgery. *Dragon Age: The Veilguard* (BioWare 2024), a game also lauded for its diverse character creator, may provide players with a “bulge slider” regardless of their chosen gender, but it does not allow avatars with a female body type to be taller than their male counterparts. In fact, even the bulge slider is limited to be smaller when playing a female character (Černoša and Ritchie 2024). The majority of character creators in games start by dividing the avatars into one of two categories—regardless of whether those categories are labelled as “male” and “female” or as “type 1” and “type 2”. These binary categories then arbitrarily determine which customization options players will be permitted. The concept behind *Your Average Character Creator*, then, was to replicate these limitations in a way that makes it obvious to players how limiting and arbitrary they are.

Gameplay in *Your Average Character Creator* is simple. Players are told that they will be creating an avatar for a video game. They are then asked to make a binary choice that, unbeknownst to them, limits all of their subsequent choices—in this case, hair colour, with the only options being blonde hair or brown hair. Already, this is intended to make players think—

why is the game not presenting them with more options? What about black hair, or red hair, or no hair? Can you dye your hair? Similar questions should of course be asked any time players are presented with a binary choice of genders. Once the hair colour has been selected, the players are then asked a series of questions regarding various physical traits, including height and weight, hair length and type, makeup, and body type. These choices are limited in various ways—for example, if someone with brown hair attempts to make a character taller than 165 cm, they are led to a screen that informs them that since people with brown hair are on average shorter than blondes, they have to be shorter. This is meant to irritate players—“on average” obviously does not mean “true of every single member of that group”, and yet that is what the game is enforcing. Players also encounter unselectable options. For example, when selecting how much makeup the character wears, players are presented with two radio buttons reading “Lots” and “None”. Players who selected brown hair will find the “None” button is already selected, and the “Lots” button is unselectable. Players who selected blonde hair will find the opposite. Additional text informs them that they are “weird” for wanting to change it, due to their hair colour. By displaying the choice in this way, players are directly confronted with the fact that the choice has already been made for them because of something completely arbitrary.

One important thing to note about the design of the game is that blonde hair and brown hair do not serve as one-to-one parallels for stereotypes around gender. While the choices themselves are limited by gendered conventions (e.g. women are short and wear makeup, men are tall and do not), both hair colours are given a mix of “male” and “female” traits. This is done in order to emphasize how arbitrary these categories are. There is nothing inherently connecting the traits “short” and “wears makeup”, and the idea that they belong under the same umbrella is a mere facet of our social construction of gender. The game challenges that by assigning these arbitrary traits to different categories.

There are many issues pervading character creators beyond their strict enforcement of the gender binary, including racism, fatphobia, ableism, and ageism. While I included some elements of these issues, I chose to focus largely on the issue of gender. This was done in part because of the potential issues around speaking for others (Alcoff 1991)—for example, as a white person, I would be likely to miss aspects of racism in character creators, and attempting to satirize those experiences could easily veer into problematic territory. Thus, I did not include skin colour as a customization option. However, I did purposefully choose to limit hair colour and texture options to ones typically associated with white people, in order to acknowledge and criticize how societal standards of beauty are frequently conflated with whiteness. The other reason I chose to focus primarily on gender was simply due to the length of the game. The

issues at hand are complex, and if I were to pack too much commentary into a short game, the message would likely be lost. Thus, while there are multiple acknowledgements of some of these other issues surrounding beauty standards, the primary focus remains on gender.

Academic Background

The major issue with character creators limited by a strict gender binary is that they do not accurately reflect gender or sex through our current understanding of both. Modern views on gender are informed by Judith Butler's concept of gender as performative: "...gender is in no way a stable identity or locus of agency from which various acts proceede [sic]; rather, it is an identity tenuously constituted in time—an identity instituted through a *stylized repetition of acts*" (Butler 1988, 519, emphasis in original). In other words, gender is not an intrinsic quality defined by one's sex or any other factor, but rather it is constructed and performed through traits that we deem to be associated with one gender or another. For example, a person's posture is in no way connected to their assigned sex at birth, but people can *perform* femininity by standing in a provocative manner, as those two things are commonly understood to be linked in modern Western culture. It follows, then, that any individual could easily choose to present themselves in different ways. Traits like the way one stands or the choice to wear makeup are not inherent qualities dependent on a person's sex, but rather choices that one makes, and thus one could choose to go against the grain if they wished. Where character creators fail is that some of these traits are not customizable, and are instead limited by a binary choice of gender or sex. Furthermore, biological sex is itself a spectrum (Viloria and Nieto 2020). Even within the ill-defined categories of "male" and "female", there is a huge amount of variation in how bodies are actually shaped. Cisgender perisex women can be tall, muscular, or stocky; they can have narrow hips, flat chests, or thick eyebrows. And yet, character creators often only present dainty, curvaceous women with soft facial features. Not to mention, there are a wide variety of medical procedures available that can result in combinations of characteristics that do not fit neatly into one category or the other. A player creating a transgender avatar will likely want more options than simply swapping the genitals on otherwise conventional depictions of men and women—why is it not possible to create a tall, broad-shouldered woman with a deep voice, or a short man with breasts and body hair? By limiting customization options in these ways, games perpetuate cultural norms of gender and sex that do not reflect the diverse reality we live in.

If these gender and sex norms are false, why do they still pervade our culture? A large part is the issue of implicit bias. Implicit bias refers to "an unconscious negative evaluation or association that gets incorporated into one's mental representation (or "schema") of a particular

concept (be it a person, group, place, even, idea, value, etc.)” (Flanagan and Kaufman 2016, 220). For example, most people unconsciously associate certain characteristics with different genders, even when they consciously know that those associations are not always true. Those biases then make their way into cultural works without their creators noticing, which perpetuates the bias. Games and those who make games are certainly not immune to these biases, particularly when the industry is still largely white men (Flanagan and Kaufman 2016, 219). To combat this, Flanagan and Kaufman have developed an Embedded Design approach which offers best practices for combating implicit biases in game design based on psychological research. They suggest that games should combine educational content with playful content, avoid imbalanced representation (e.g. a balanced gender team of characters is more effective than a majority-female one), include repetition to reinforce the concepts, and avoid making the messaging too obvious (2016, 226-227). *Your Average Character Creator* is designed with this framework in mind. The game strives to balance its message with comedic elements, and does not portray itself as a serious game, with its purposeful limitations not becoming obvious until later in the game. By employing this framework, games like *Your Average Character Creator* may be able to help counteract internalized prejudices and help players to recognize biases both in games and in the real world.

This concept of using games to enact social change is part of a larger movement known as “games-for-change”. The games-for-change movement, largely spearheaded by Jane McGonigal and her book *Reality is Broken* (2012), promotes the idea that games can “serve as a backdrop for serious collaboration, thinking, and reflection” (Egenfeldt-Nielsen et al. 2012, 267). As a huge and ever-growing part of the media landscape, games have the potential to serve as forces for improving our lives. As McGonigal puts it, “[w]e can no longer afford to view games as separate from our real lives and our real work. It is not only a waste of the potential of games to do real good—it is simply untrue. ... Games aren’t leading us to the downfall of human civilization. They’re leading us to its reinvention” (McGonigal 2012, 354). While small in scale, *Your Average Character Creator* was designed with this idea in mind—by challenging players to recognize the implicit gender-based biases in both games and in themselves, the game will hopefully encourage players to continue to recognize those biases in other circumstances and fight to work against them.

Design Process

These frameworks and principles all informed the design process of *Your Average Character Creator*. In designing the game, I chose to make it text-based. This was largely because creating customizable visuals would require a good deal of time, effort, and skill, but it

was also because of the possibility of players being biased by visuals that they read as gendered—an issue I still ran into, which I will discuss in more depth later. Because I wanted a text-based interface with some basic interactive options, I decided to work in Twine and add customizable options through HTML/CSS as needed.

The development process was relatively straightforward once those decisions were made. First, I decided what customization options the user would have, starting with hair colour as the stand-in for gender. I then picked other characteristics based on what was typical of character creators, what could be easily implemented, and what characteristics were typically limited by gender or other idealized beauty standards in character creators. For example, I chose to let the player customize nose and eyebrow type, as those characteristics are often (completely arbitrarily) linked to gender, with women not being permitted to have thick eyebrows or large noses. I also included a few other choices that were not necessarily limited by gender, but by other beauty standards. For example, it is not possible to select a large or crooked nose, despite those being very common features in real people. The game also includes a hidden BMI calculation when the player inputs their height and weight, and rejects any characters that are deemed to be “overweight”. BMI has no clear relation to health (Gutin 2018), and there is no reason to limit the build or weight of a character in a supposedly customizable character creator. Those who may protest on the basis of “realism”, arguing that overweight characters would not be able to perform the feats of athleticism that many video game protagonists perform, are not only incorrect in making this assumption—many top athletes could be considered “overweight” (Bishara 2015)—but they are also ignoring that many games are a fantasy, not based in realism, and even a skinny person could not shoot fireballs from their hands. This aspect of *Your Average Character Creator* is intended to bring attention to this issue as well, on top of its concerns around gender.

Once I had compiled a reasonable prototype of the game, I decided to search for character creators for inspiration on what further options I could add. I was immediately met with this screen:

Figure 3: The introductory screen from charactercreator.org.

I did not bother to continue past this screen, as I was already sufficiently inspired (and irritated). As is clear in Figure 3, the actual physical differences between the “male” and “female” body types in this character creator are quite subtle. The man has slightly broader shoulders, and the woman has slightly broader hips. However, to avoid any user accidentally getting the correct impression that the differences between male and female bodies are quite small, this creator has chosen to pose the female option in an overtly sexualized manner, whereas the male option stands in a neutral pose. Not only does this reinforce ideas of male as the default, but it also perpetuates the idea that people of different sexes are not only physically different but are also fundamentally and inherently different in personality and the way that they present themselves to the world. As previously discussed, this is not true. It is, however, something seen very commonly in video games, where female characters are posed and animated with a specific (often sexualized) physicality that is never given to the male characters. Thus, I decided to include a “pose” option in order to call attention to this discrepancy.

Once I assembled my list of customization options, it was a straightforward process to type up the options into Twine and set up the various checks and limitations on the options.

Figure 4: The Twine structure for *Your Average Character Creator*.

To disable options and limit choices, I used HTML/CSS. The most complicated bit of code is the BMI calculator that uses a simple calculation to determine if the given height and weight fall into the “overweight” category or not. I made the choice to not limit how small the acceptable weights could be, because societal pressures overwhelmingly push people to lose weight regardless of whether weighing so little is safe or healthy. Other than that, the actual code behind the project is generally simple, with each button leading to the next node and storing the value of the selected option as a variable. Most of the effort was put into the writing, in order to create choices that conveyed to the player how they were being unfairly limited, just as they would be in real character creators.

Playtesting and Feedback

After a prototype of the game was completed, I sent it to a variety of playtesters. The specific questions I asked were, “What do you think the game is about?”, “What did you feel when playing the game?”, “Were there any parts of the game that confused you?”, and “Any other feedback you’d like to provide?”. My intention was to determine whether the meaning of the game came across to players, and whether the experience evoked the feelings of frustration it was meant to evoke. As well, I wanted to see if there were areas of the game that could be

improved upon. The results from the playtesters, which are included in the appendix, were mixed. While some people easily grasped the underlying point of the game as a critique of unfair limitations in character creators, fewer connected that critique to gender, and some missed the point entirely. This did not completely surprise me, as I was not sure if the game's point would come across to anyone who is unaccustomed to questioning gender stereotypes. However, there were more people who missed the point than I was expecting, so I decided to make several changes in order to better convey my intent.

First, I decided to add more explicit references to hair colour in order to convey to the player the reason why their choices are being limited. Multiple players expressed confusion over options being greyed out or unselectable with no explanation as to why the options were not selectable. While these options only appear later in the game and I had hoped that players would have encountered enough descriptions previously for them to glean why they were being limited, playtesting led me to realize that it is possible to only choose options that are deemed acceptable and so do not trigger additional text explaining the "reasoning" behind the arbitrary limitations. As such, I decided to add more flavour text to choices where options were limited, giving the player an option to click on text to express their confusion and receive an "answer". Furthermore, I added more explicit references to hair colour in particular, so that the player can easily understand that all of these limitations are based on that first arbitrary choice.

Secondly, some players expressed confusion over how gender was being portrayed. I made the decision to not have hair colour be a one-to-one stand-in for gender—that is, in this game, blond is not "male" and brown hair is not "female", or vice versa. However, the pose image in particular cued players into thinking they were creating a female or male character, as the models were somewhat gendered. This then confused some players, since players who picked blonde hair were asked about bra sizes followed by images of bodies they perceived as male, leading players to assume that these bodies would not have breasts. While this will be difficult to avoid completely, as visual conceptions of gendered norms are highly engrained, I made two changes to attempt to make my intentions clearer. First, I swapped the personality descriptions in the final summary, so that the "female" description would be presented next to the "male" pose, and vice versa. This was to make it clearer that the discrepancies are a deliberate choice and not a bug. Secondly, I replaced the pose images with simple figure drawings, in order to further remove any gendered associations with the visuals.

Figure 5: Comparison of the pose selection screen before and after playtester feedback. Poses taken from PoseMyArt.

Finally, I wanted to address the fact that it is possible to go through the game without running into any limitations, if the player's choices happen to align with the expectations for a character with their chosen hair colour. I did this by adding more flavour text to questions with unselectable options, thus making it more obvious that these options are unselectable for a reason, and removing some "neutral" options in order to increase the likelihood that players encounter an obstacle. While this works as a partial solution, with more time I would want to add more options to reduce the odds of this happening, and potentially implement something to encourage players to create multiple characters. This is an area that would require more playtesting and time in order to address properly.

Overall, based on the feedback from playtesters, I would say that the game did succeed for some players. Several reported feeling "seething rage and kinda gross" or other similar expressions of frustration, which is of course what I was intending. It was clear to players that this was a critique, and many reported feeling amused alongside frustration, so I would say that the game succeeded as a work of satire. One player commented, "If it had been a 'real'

character builder in a real game, with the same limitations (and without the snark) I would have felt offended that my body was illegal and annoyed with the overly sexualized results, but since this was clearly a critique, I didn't feel the same way". This is again what I was hoping the results would be. The game is meant to make the player uncomfortable and limit them in ways that they do not like, in order to bring attention to how real character creators do the same thing. However, as mentioned, some players seemed more confused than uncomfortable about their lack of options. While my goal is to make players uncomfortable, I chose to remedy this issue through added clarity rather than added discomfort, as according to feedback from some playtesters ("I am THIS close to ragequitting your game", sent to me by DM while playing) it was already sufficiently uncomfortable to those who understood it.

Limitations and Successes

One area in which future renditions of the game could be improved would be to implement a way to force the player to go through the process multiple times. This would not only help avoid the issue of players missing the game's limitations, but would also help reinforce the point the game is trying to make through repetition, as recommended by Flanagan and Kaufman (2016). It would also allow players to better understand the point of the game, as they would be able to see the impact of various choices more clearly. A potential way to go about this would be to ask the player to create a small party of characters, rather than just a single avatar.

Another way the game was limited was its small scope. As mentioned previously, there are a wide variety of issues plaguing character creators beyond gender-based ones. These issues are equally deserving of critique, and if the game had a larger scale, perhaps it could address those issues as well in greater detail without muddying the message. Another option would be to create a series of similar games, each with a specific focus.

Despite the game's initial flaws and its continued limitations, the game did succeed for some players. Playtesters expressed frustration with the lack of choices, and reflected that the game was commenting on beauty standards and representations of bodies and particularly women in games, which indicates that the game was successfully making them think about these issues. One tester even commented, "...this really is your average character creator", showing that they could see the connection between the exaggerated limitations in this game and the real character creators that it aims to critique. With some further refinement to encourage repetition, the game will hopefully encourage anyone who plays it to reflect on character creators in games and the restrictive societal structures that influence them.

Conclusion

Your Average Character Creator is a simple game, but one with an important message. Despite the seemingly large number of customization options, most character creators in games still enforce a strict gender binary, limiting players to extremely specific ideas of what men and women can look like that do not reflect the real diversity in the world around us. In the real world, women can be tall and broad-shouldered. Men can be slight and have softer features. Transgender, non-binary, and intersex people all exist, and can have any combination of physical features. People can be fat, old, or disabled. By restricting players to one of two strictly defined body types, character creators not only unfairly limit players' ability to customize and express themselves through their avatar, but they also perpetuate false ideas about the gender binary and what people should look like. When even a medium that claims to offer choice does not present the choice to be anything other than a tall, muscular man or a short, curvy woman, it pushes the idea that these are the only possibilities—which in turn alienates anyone who does not match those expectations. Given that that is the majority of the population, this seems problematic. If a real character creator limited players the way *Your Average Character Creator* does, based on hair colour, there would be massive outcry. That outcry should be no less quiet when the customization options are limited by gender instead.

Appendix

What do you think the game is about?	What did you feel when playing the game?	Were there any parts of the game that confused you?	Any other feedback you'd like to provide?
Statistical Assumptions? And making a character!	I laughed a couple times, but really wanted to be taller..	Makeup wasn't selectable	Enjoyed the comedic aspect
misogyny, the sexualization of women in society, the harsh and specific beauty standards and expectations set for them, and the lack of diversity options and representation of how women are portrayed in media and games	seething rage and kinda gross		
Directions to common stereotypes with characters and appearances.	Surprised that tall and brunets don't mix.	Nothing much on confusing. It's a good start for a game design.	Only issue was scrolling problems. Originally also mobile issues however it was later discussed that this is designed for a computer.
Giving the illusion of choice over things that don't matter to distract you from how little control you have.	Fun at first, sliding towards irritation and frustration as choices became more restrictive	The first grayed out answer. And also the fact that at no point did it ask for gender - I think it was forcing it into a female type character?	for answers where they have to type in the numbers, maybe have it auto remove the 0 in the box. not a big deal but i entered in weights like 050 kg. also maybe provide an option to enter in feet/inches or lbs. it would have been funny if at the end there was like. a pixelated sprite where the hair covers the eyes and weight/height/half the questions dont matter at all. the only thing that changes is which

			pose theyre in and the hair colour/length.
<p>Top level - how character creators often pretend to give you lots of control over your appearance, but actually still force you into a narrow range of body types and presentations. Slightly deeper, it's also a reflection on how these character builders can reinforce/promote gender expectations and stereotypes (and binaries), not to mention make anyone who falls outside of their narrow zone (i.e. most people) feel lacking and/or excluded for having bodies that don't meet those standards.</p>	<p>Mostly I was curious as to where it was going. I enjoyed the experience of making choices the game deemed too ridiculous, because it was fun to try to figure out the parameters and read the snarky comments. If it had been a "real" character builder in a real game, with the same limitations (and without the snark) I would have felt offended that my body was illegal and annoyed with the overly sexualized results, but since this was clearly a critique, I didn't feel the same way. Except maybe when it said my hair made me automatically unattractive - i laughed, but also felt put out. Oh, and I HATED the choices of standing poses for the blond/female.</p>	<p>Yes. I played twice, and picked blond the first time, and ended up with a very female looking body. Second time, I picked brown hair, and the choices that were unacceptable for blonds worked, so I assumed I was now building a stereotypical male body, and I hadn't really made any choices that didn't work to show me otherwise. So the question about cup size threw me, especially since the standing pose that came after did show a stereotypical male video game hero body. I thought it might have been a bug.</p> <p>After I played a few more times I developed a better sense of what was going on. If I had made different choices in my first run, it would have</p>	<p>I loved/hated the "click here when you are happy with your choice" buttons when I was not given a choice/not allowed my preferred choice/all choices were terrible. that's mean. well done.</p> <p>I wonder if there would be a way to force the player to build more than one character and/or increase the odds they try to pick something "wrong". Perhaps "0 kg" should not be a valid weight? (but perhaps it should!)</p>

		<p>been more obvious, but "blonds are tall" just made me think scandinavian, not female, so I just felt like I was building a random character and trying to figure out what the mysterious limitations on "blond" were.</p>	
<p>story based game where your appearance affects how npcs treat you</p>	<p>confused why i couldnt choose some options</p>	<p>wanting to choose specific options but they are greyed out</p>	<p>i kind of was expecting a comment about the 0 KG option from the comments on the other options lol. should totally have skin color option lol</p>
<p>Stereotypes</p>	<p>Amused</p>	<p>Only long enough to make me laugh</p>	<p>Green hair. Red eyes.</p>
<p>A scathing review of the flaws in actual character designers</p>	<p>Amused. In a 'wow that's so rude, but I know you are doing it On Purpose, so it's kinda funny, but also it's real enough I am almost offended?'</p>	<p>Some answers were not selectable at all, but there was no commentary about them being unchoosable, so I was left uncertain if that was the point. Plus I wanted to hear the reasoning behind why some might have been 'not allowed' for my type.</p> <p>Also I was slightly surprised when choosing cup size, as I thought I'd be told I was designing a female character,</p>	<p>It was fun! Snark was amusing, and also some 'ouch, that's too real' in a good way.</p>

		especially since gender is very much a part of the flaws of this type of system	
How bodies are represented in games, how restrictive, unrealistic and stereotypical they are	Annoyed about the lack of choices and being told what kind of character I can be		
I think the game is about the limitations of character creation and how these constraints can be based on perceived beauty standards.	After the first question when I pressed the other option button and there weren't any, I felt quite limited in my choices, but also validated in a way. I think this is the kind of vague feeling I have sometimes when creating characters on other platforms, but in this game it's more pronounced. In the end when the game says "Isn't customization fun?" I thought that it was funny since it wasn't really that customizable, and that this really is your average character creator.	N/a	When I tried to go back and see my choices, or replay the game, it would go back to the ending for the original run of the game, but maybe this is part of the limiting aspect of the game or maybe because I played it on my phone?

Works Cited

- Alcoff, Linda. 1991. "The Problem of Speaking for Others." *Cultural Critique* (20): 5-32.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/1354221>.
- BioWare. 2024. *Dragon Age: The Veilguard*. Electronic Arts.
- Bishara, Motez. 2015. "Fat or fit? These 'obese' athletes are proud of their extra pounds." *CNN*, May 20, 2015. <https://edition.cnn.com/2015/05/18/sport/overweight-athletes-sabathia-davis-feat>.
- Butler, Judith. 1988. "Performative Acts and Gender Constitution: An Essay in Phenomenology and Feminist Theory." *Theatre Journal* 40(4): 519-531.
- Carette, Eileen. 2025. *Your Average Character Creator*. Available at <https://eyeofthedragon.itch.io/your-average-character-creator>.
- CD Projekt Red. 2020. *Cyberpunk 2077*. CD Projekt.
- Černoša, Ada and Verity "verilybitchie" Ritchie. 2024. "Video Games & the Sexy Gender Binary." Video essay published on YouTube, 30:09.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GhhJ27S7H3M>.
- Egenfeldt-Nielsen, Simon, Jonas Heide Smith, and Susana Pajares Tosca. 2007. *Understanding Video Games*. Routledge.
- Flanagan, Mary and Geoff Kaufman. 2016. "Shifting Implicit Biases With Games Using Psychology." In *Diversifying Barbie and Mortal Kombat: Intersectional Perspectives and Inclusive Designs in Gaming*, edited by Yasmin B. Kafai, Gabriela T. Richard, and Brendesha M. Tynes. ETC Press.

- Gutin, Iliya. 2018. "In BMI we trust: reframing the body mass index as a measure of health." *Soc Theory Health* 16: 256-271. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41285-017-0055-0>
- Larian Studios. 2023. *Baldur's Gate 3*. Larian Studios.
- McGonigal, Jane. 2012. *Reality is Broken: Why Games Make Us Better and How They Can Change the World*. Vintage Books.
- Studio Chacre. 2014-2023. *The Character Creator*. charactercreator.org.
- Viloria, Hida and Maria Nieto. 2020. *The Spectrum of Sex: The Science of Male, Female, and Intersex*. Jessica Kingsley Publishers.